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Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
European Research Infrastructure Consortium

Training at CESSDA: Involvement of librarians

Irena Vipavc Brvar

CESSDA Training WG Leader

European Diversity of CESSDA SPs

Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives

3 primary communities:

- Data producers
- Data users
- Professionals at Service Providers

-> Train the research community throughout the research lifecycle.

■ Members

16 +1

■ Partners

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Expert tour guide on Data Management

Local diversity

Expert tips

cessda.eu/DMGuide

Librarians could
Support researchers

Obstacles:

- lack knowledge
- confidence
- overloaded

Presentations
and exercises

social scientists

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Role of librarian in RDM

- Provides information about the availability of existing data sources.
- Supports preparation of formal DMPs.
- Provides information about options to deposit data in a data centre or data archive.
- Provides information about open access conditions and advantages.
- Provides support with preparation of basic study metadata and documentation, author's rights, and explains other deposition requirements.
- Provides information about accessioning datasets into a bibliographic system for the purpose of scientific evaluation and resource discovery.
- Provides data citation guidance.
- Provides information about linking data with publications and research projects.

Future events and work

RDM Expert Tour Guide: [Train the Trainers Workshop](#) / 12 – 13 April / Ljubljana, Slovenia

Local RMD training events

CESSDA Workshop: Exploring data in Europe - with a focus on European attitudes and Value / 29 May / Prague, Czech Republic

Data Discovery workshop at 3 summer schools

CESSDA Data Catalogue

CESSDA Knowledge Platform

Training

Training focuses on 'train the trainers' and new modes of sharing expertise

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